

BIODIVERSITY OF DESERT PLANTS

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Abstract. Currently, climate change is causing changes in the desert vegetation's biodiversity. This has led to a significant reduction in the species composition of desert grassland vegetation, and the results of the investigations shows that in pasture reserves the composition of the species may increase into 4-6 by forming micro-climates.

Keywords: desert pastures, biodiversity, reservation, forest resources, psammophite and gypsum plant.

БИОРАЗНООБРАЗИЕ ПУСТЫННЫХ РАСТЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В настоящее время изменение климата вызывает изменения в биоразнообразии пустынной растительности. Это привело к значительному сокращению видового состава растительности пастбищ пустынь, и результаты исследований показывают, что в пастбищных заповедниках состав видов может увеличиться до 4-6 за счет формирования микроклимата.

Ключевые слова: пустынные пастбища, биоразнообразие, лесные ресурсы, псаммофит и гипсофил.

ЧЎЛ ЎСИМЛИКЛАРИ БИОХИЛМАХИЛЛИГИ

Аннотация. Ҳозирги вақтдаги иқлим ўзгаришлари чўл ўсимликлари биохилмахиллигининг ўзгаришига сабаб бўлмоқда. Бу эса, чўл яйлов ўсимликлари тур таркибининг қисқаришига олиб келмоқда. Тадқиқот натижаларига кўра, қўриқланадиган яйлов ҳудудларида микроиқлимнинг шаклланиши ҳисобига ўсимлик турлари сонини 4-6 тагача ошириши мумкин

Калит сўзлар: чўл яйловлари, биохилмахиллик, ўрмон ресурслари, псаммофит ва гипсофил.

Introduction. To provide the full and rational use of rich forest resources of the Republic, further improvement of forestry management system, to increase of efficiency of use of forest resources, introduction of advanced scientific and technical achievements in the field, strengthening and modernization of material and technical base of forestry, to attract more active foreign investments and develop the ecological system [1] the State Committee for Forestry of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established.

Most of the territory of Uzbekistan is desert, with its flora and its growing conditions. Desert areas consist mainly of deserts such as Kyzylkum, Karakum, Mirzachul and Karshi desert. Growing plants here are subdivided into psammophite, gypsum, and halophyte, depending on soil conditions. In areas with high content of sand, psammophytes and gypsum plaster halophyte plants [2]. grow.

The Southern Kyzylkum climate has poor saline, gypsum, sandy loam soils for plant growth. On sandy soils, an environmental group of psammophytes is formed, where the tree grows from one year to the next. The sandy desert shrub vegetation consists of more than 60 associations of white saxaul (*Haloxylon persicum*), cherkes (*Salsola richteri*), rabbit (*Ammodendron conolyi*) and mixed saxaul (*Haloxylon persicum*, *Haloxylon aphyllum*).

Auxiliary species to these associations are tree or shrub species of corn (*Calligonum eripodum*, *C. caput-medusae*, *C. microcarpum*, *C. setosum*, *C. leucocladum*), various bushes-astragal (*Astragalus villosissimis*, *A. unifolilatus*), aralicus (*Arbusculus*), a coniferous shrub and perennial grasses (*Convolvulus wallicatus*, *C. Korolkovii*), mothole (*Mausolea eriocarpa*), ore (*Artemisia diffusa*, *A. turanica*, *A. terra-albae*), chogon (*Halothamnus subaphyllus*), ephemeroide (*Physodes*), reven (*Rheum turkestanicum*), beetle (*Poa bulbosa*), beetle (*Ferula assa-foetida*), short-term grasses — *Tithymalus densis*, *Agriophyllum latifolium*, *A. minus*, *Corispermum lehmannianum*, *Salsola paulserha*, *S. solerha*, *Eremopyrum distans*, *E. Orientalis*, *E. Buonapartii*, *Senecio subden tetus*, *Malcolmia grandiflora*, *M. Africana*, *Isatis violascans*, *I. Minima*, *Spirorhynchus Sabulogus*, *Tetracme recurvata*, *Streptoloma desertorum*, *Sohismus arabicus*, *Matricaria lomellata* grows and develops [3-6]

In low-sandy sands, gypophyll plants of the psammophyte plants are represented by the masses of turpentine (*Artemisia turanica*), dyes (*Salsola arbuscula*), astragal (*Astragalus villosissimis*, *A. unifolilatus*), partek (*Convolvulus wallicatus*, *C. Korolkovii*). In severe saline soils, one-year-old saline-resistant plant species (*Artemisia turanica*, *Gamonthus gamocarpus*, *Halimocnemis longifolia*), versatile dew, dye, psammophytic plants (*Calligonum microcarpum*, *Conoculture*, *Ephephalus*, and *Leucochyllocellus*). hamodoe, *C. wallicatus*) [6].

In South Kyzylkum, plant transformation is depend on relief and this process is changing by human impact. As a result of the grazing of livestock, the creation of various economic facilities, and the inefficient use of agricultural land, the natural vegetation is decreasing.

Research method. Dynamics of plant formation in phytocenosis was studied in 10 experimental fields. In each phytocenosis, for systematic observations of the dynamics and development of the plant, 3 continuous transects located between the rows were selected.

To control the difference from the other fields, 4 control transects with a size of 50x2 m were selected. In each transect, a total report about the species and quantitative composition was made three times in a year in spring, summer, and autumn.

Research results and their discussion. The phytocenosis of the plants under study has changed over the course of development. At the same time, the condition of the plants that make up the local flora improved, and their density and quantity increased. The number of species has increased due to shrubs, semi-shrubs, semi-annual and perennial grasses.

In the spring, ephemeral and ephemeroide dominated the orange (*Bromus tectorum* L) and were the dominant ones. The observations revealed that the number of spring plants was 1.1-9.8 times higher than the control variant. In the soil of the soil 1-1 phytocenosis 1,1-8,4 times the control variant, 2-phytocenosis in weak sandy soils 2,3-8,1 times the control variant and 6,8- in the 4-phytocenosis in the brown soils 9.8 times higher.

During the summer season, grass-vegetation, perennial grasses and shrubs were the main focus of spring and summer. Their role was high in the extent of vegetation and soil cover. The growth of the plants by late spring had a negative effect on the growth of plants, with the vegetation

being 1.1-5.4 times higher than the control variant. In summer, the amount of plants from other natural and artificial phytocenoses is 2.1-2.5 times higher than the control variants in dense soils, 2.3-2.6 and 2.3 times higher than the control variants on weakly developed sandy soils. 4-phytocenosis in brown soils was 2,6-5,4 times higher than the control variant.

In autumn, the vegetation was mainly concentrated on shrubs, semi-shrubs and perennial grasses. During this season, the effect of vegetation was 1.3–3.7 times higher than the control variants. Significant increase in the amount of vegetation compared to the control variants was due to a sharp increase in July – August temperature (45oC) and loss of moisture in the soil surface layer. This season, the phytocenosis counts mentioned above are also high.

Conclusion. It has been observed that they also affect the composition of plants, as well as their composition. In the area, plants such as pistachio, astragal, and cobwebs have declined, and instead have increased the number of plants such as lilac, chagan, teresken and izen. In addition, it was found that there were 5-8 species of plants growing in the area at the time of the conservation, and now about 25-30 species are growing in the area. Among these species, we can see that 4-6 species naturally formed. This has led to the fact that by creating a reserve, it is possible not only to increase the number of plants in the area but also to increase their species composition.

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